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THE ROLE OF THE INTERNET IN TOURIST PROMOTION

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ABSTRACT

The modern age brings many changes in all spheres of life, and therefore also in business, especially when it comes to tourism. In a globalized and extremely dynamic environment, the holders of tourist offers are faced with changes - in the structure of tourists, the geographical and temporal distribution of tourist flows. Accordingly, the permanent changes in the requirements, tastes and expectations of the modern tourist force tourism entities to include innovations as a key element of their offer in order to achieve competitiveness in the tourism market. Given the fact that tourism is an activity based on constant communications between participants in tourist flows, the maintenance and development of this activity relies on information, so the development of the destination increasingly depends on the ability to monitor and adapt to modern trends and the ability to master new technologies. Internet content provides various promotional amenities for tourism that significantly influence tourists' decision-making. Today, modern tourists start their journey by opening websites related to attractive places and potential destinations, accommodation facilities, transportation, attractive contents and places to be visited during the trip and other animations with which the experience would be complete.

The purpose of this paper is to perceive the possibilities offered by the Internet for promoting the tourist offer in the global tourist market. It will process the tools of this global network that represent modern promotional channels for

promotion and increasing the effectiveness in promoting the tourist offer at different levels.

KEY WORDS: promotion, promotional media, internet, smart tourism, social networks

INTRODUCTION

Tourism has experienced significant progress in all its segments in recent decades. The strong basis for positive changes is of course the permanent advancement of technology, creating a constructive platform for simple, fast and secure communication. Modern communication requires the support of sophisticated technology and has established itself as a standard in order to follow the current trends. In this section, an important place is occupied by the Internet - a virtual medium that, due to its characteristics, has found wide application in the social and business life of people. It has become such a powerful and useful element of everyday life that it is almost impossible to imagine life without it.

The Internet has created a world without borders, in which information becomes available at any time and in any place. The use of the Internet is also evident in tourism, through better connections between many places and ease of organizing trips. It enables the tourist offer to create and offer a diverse range of products and services and bring them closer to demand with a targeted reach to the customers. At the social level, the Internet has caused certain deviations in behavior, but it has brought them virtually closer and allowed users to communicate closely. Recently, this communication has been done through various social networks, where, in addition to direct communication, experiences are exchanged according to various areas of interest.

Tourism is an activity that relies heavily on information, so the development of destinations increasingly depends on the ability to follow and adapt to modern trends and the rapid adaptation and ability to master new technologies. Internet tourism provides various benefits from marketing and targeted business operations that significantly influence tourists' decisions.

THE IMPACT OF THE INTERNET ON THE TOURISM DEVELOPMENT

The Internet is the largest, global computer network which, due to its global nature, is very quickly being accepted and used in presenting and showcasing the content of the destination's tourism product. It breaks down time and space barriers and brings tourism values closer to every potential tourist. The Internet can be identified as a network that is composed of millions of computer domestic and international networks and enables data transfer between computers, which drastically reduces the cost of information, mutual communication, and overcoming time and space limitations. The development of information technology allows the Internet to represent a "network of all networks" consisting of millions of domestic, academic, business, government, non-governmental, research, health, banking and other networks between which data and information are exchanged in the form of services and documents that use basic Internet services. This character allows access to a huge amount of data at any time and from any place, which allows the user of global access, i.e. entities in the tourism industry, to obtain information based on which they will make appropriate decisions. The Internet can help all tourism product carriers to gain a new opportunity for successful promotion and for selling services and products, and to align with the demands, needs and desires of consumers. Therefore, the theory clearly emphasizes that the Internet represents an interesting and useful distribution channel for finding customers and provides the ability to identify their desires (Vassos T., 1999). As a global network that connects everyone on the planet, the Internet offers the fastest, most creative and easiest way to connect tourism providers with potential guests. It is a major support for the progress and development of tourism and hospitality around the world, as well it as an opportunity to bring tourist destinations closer to guests than ever before. At the same time, it is the cheapest way to present the values, the wide range of offers and the benefits that the destination offers, giving the opportunity to the holders of the tourist offer for best presentation of their offer and to encourage the guest's desire for visiting that destination. Given the fact that tourism relies to a large extent on information, the tourist development of destinations increasingly depends on the ability to follow and adapt to modern trends, the rapid adaptation and the ability to master new technologies.

Internet network simultaneously enables the formation of a feedback loop between tourism supply and demand, and tourism workers can very easily and quickly access data of tourists' desires, needs and demands, find out what attracts guests the most, what elements are missing or represent a weak link in

the supply chain, so that they can quickly react and adjust their offer. By setting up and upgrading a website, every tourist entity can constantly inform both potential and existing guests about the content and additional privileges, discounts, and arrangements that are offered and available to guests. Compared to before, where tourists visited well-known destinations or recommended destinations with positive experiences passed on "by word of mouth" from their relatives and friends, today they can independently organize their travel and stay, according to their interests and needs. Hence, although the Internet is considered the second most important medium of promotion after television, it can be said that it takes first place as the "most relaxed and interesting medium".

Internet has many advantages as a channel for transmitting the promotion message (Kotler, et al., 2010, p. 502):

- ✓ Fast and simple transmission of the tourist offer;
- ✓ Fast and affordable media;
- ✓ Offers additional benefits and discounts;
- ✓ Offers possibility for creating a complete picture of the tourist destination;
- ✓ Enables streaming and live broadcast;
- ✓ Getting quick feedback from potential tourists;
- ✓ Establishment of strong direct interaction relations of the holders of tourist offer with tourists;
- ✓ The content of the promotion message can be changed quickly and simply;
- ✓ The Internet turns every tourist company and other holder of a tourist offer (local or national) into an "office" with 24-hour working hours;
- ✓ The costs of production, organization and distribution of the presentations are much lower compared to other media.

It is also important to mention its impact on prices, as well as the intensification of the competitive battle between tourist destinations. Such modern conditions impose the need for greater innovation in creating and presenting the message, but also creating more attractive offers in order to survive in the tourist market. Therefore, since the mid-nineties of the last century, the tourist industry has accepted and applied the Internet as a distribution channel but also as an effective promotional channel that, with its tools, provides broad opportunities for presenting the destination product on the global tourist market.

AREAS OF INFLUENCE OF THE INTERNET ON TOURISM

The Internet has an impact on three segments in the tourism sector – providers of tourism services (hotels, airlines, car and boat rental companies), intermediaries in tourism trade (tour operators and travel agencies) which design and sell travel packages, and tourists as consumers.

The following changes that the emergence of the Internet is causing in tourism can be highlighted (Zekanović L., Klarin, T., 2012, pp. 59-72):

- affects the disappearance of intermediaries;
- with the Internet, new intermediaries appear, and traditional intermediaries must change their roles;
- direct access to tourists is ensured;
- immediate transmission of reliable information is ensured;
- it is possible to display the state of business activity in real time;
- costs for organization and distribution are reduced;
- convenience and flexibility in presentation are increased;
- emerge of new channels for direct sales in the tourism industry.

At the same time, the Internet has increased the possibility for both sides of the tourism market - "tourism service producers" and tourists - to influence on the level of prices as well as increasing rivalry between existing competitors. In such conditions, enterprises in the tourism sector are forced to be innovative in order to ensure competitiveness in the tourism market.

The Internet network fulfills its role in communication processes through its five basic tools:

1. WWW - World Wide Web - The World Wide Web, or simply WWW, is the youngest information service on the Internet. It is a system that allows pages containing text, images, sound, animation, and video to be published or read from a computer connected to the Internet. The Web is a multimedia and interactive form of communication. Multimedia means that it can be used to create information text, image and sound, all in dynamic situations. Interactive means that the user intervenes in the message by expressing his interest in the content of the message. In a propaganda message that is distributed through mass media, the user receives content that the sender believes to be true and the recipient is not given the opportunity for any intervention. The web space is filled with four basic types of users: customers -

consumers, companies or individuals who create programs or make them available to customers, companies that use the network for promotion, and companies that create programs and tools to operate more efficiently in this expanding market.

2. E-mail - Electronic mail allows computer users around the world to exchange messages through their E-mail addresses.
3. FTP - File Transfer Protocol, is a standard communication protocol used for the transfer of computer files from a server to a client on a computer network;
4. IRChat - Internet Relay Chat, is a text-based chat system for instant messaging. IRC is designed for group communication in discussion forums, called channels;
5. News groups - Usenet, is a worldwide distributed discussion system available on computers, where millions of computer users share information on various topics by monitoring messages sent to a specific group.

APPLICATION OF THE INTERNET IN TOURISM THROUGH SMART TOURISM

Tourism is one of the activities that is facing the most transformations today, especially with the emergence of so called Internet of things – as a multidimensional data system. Internet of things enables the interconnection of physical things – facilities, objects, vehicles, tourist attractions and phenomena with digital systems and their joint action in a direct and interactive connection between tourists, tourist services and destinations. This

system, together with the increasingly intensive development of information technology, encourages the emergence of the concept of Smart Tourism. The concept of Smart Tourism represents a new area of technology that offers wide possibilities for action and constant upgrading. It allows the development of information and communication infrastructure through the use of websites, internet portals, travel-related websites, smartphones, and social media. Its application is seen in the following (Брдар, И., et al., 2018):

- Personal wellness monitoring of tourists: sensors for monitoring physiological parameters (blood pressure, blood sugar level, stress, heart rate) which is directly related to health tourism, i.e. medical tourism;
- Geolocation of tourists and tourist groups;
- Personalized services for tourists;
- Health protection during travel. Internet technology can monitor the development of infectious diseases/pandemics and to separate or direct infected tourists while the competent services offer health protection, as well as respond in a timely manner in the event of epidemics/pandemics (e.g. Covid 19 pandemic);
- Customs services/visa regime – facilitation of international travel, issuance of travel documents, customs etc.;
- Smart hotels to Smart cities – which apply IT solutions in offering tourist services, from promotion of the tourist destination, reservations, insurance, animations to reducing operating costs for lighting, alternative energy sources, traffic, ecology, etc.

CURRENT INTERNET TOOLS IN TOURISM

Modern tourists begin their journey by opening websites related to attractive places and potential destinations. By studying their content, they obtain information about the destination, accommodation capacity, type of transport by which they can reach the destinations, attractions and places to visit during the trip in order to fully complement the trip and expand the experience. In order for successful promotion, the holders of a tourist offer cannot be known, interesting and chosen by tourists if they do not have their own website or profile on social networks. They can also use the services of digital agencies such as specialized internet marketing agencies in tourism, which deal with marketing activities, brand promotion, and increase sales using new technologies. The services offered by these agencies in the tourism sector are (Explicit design):

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- ✓ creating websites;
 - ✓ mobile application development;
 - ✓ development of specialized CMS (Content Management System) software that serve for easy maintenance of the website or mobile application;
 - ✓ creation of interactive maps for the region with marked attractions and other important locations;
 - ✓ marking of pedestrian and bicycle paths;
 - ✓ prize games on Social Networks and promotional applications that will increase the number of followers on the page;
 - ✓ development of tourist portals;
 - ✓ Internet advertising;
 - ✓ special benefits notification systems (SMS messages and Newsletter);
 - ✓ quality and secure VPS / Dedicated server.

To maintain competitiveness in the tourism market, tourism service providers, in coordination with digital internet marketing agencies, are constantly looking for something new and interesting in order to attract and retain the attention of tourists. Some of the most creative and innovative solutions and trends that are expanding and upgrading are (Vodič za korišćenje..., 2017): Content marketing, Virtual tours, social networks Facebook, Instagram, Twitter, Booking and Trip advisor platforms.

LEVEL OF PROMOTION OF OHRID'S TOURIST OFFER

The tourism promotion of the municipality of Ohrid takes place on several levels. Accommodation facilities, as basic receptive factors, independently promote their offer using the usual internet platforms used for tourist promotion, such as Booking.com, AirBnB, Trip Advisor, as well as through their official website. This level also includes the promotion of destination facilities and other natural and cultural values by travel agencies that placed the offer on the market as their product.

The promotion of the tourist product of Ohrid is also carried out at the local level, through the representation of tourist values within the official website of the local administration of the municipality as well as on several internet platforms

(<https://ohrid.gov.mk/category/tourism>, <https://ohridtouristassociation.com/>).

Other level of promotion is through the propaganda material and publications produced by the Agency for the Promotion and Support of Tourism in Republic of Macedonia, presented in printed form, and through the Agency's official website (<http://tourismmacedonia.gov.mk/>)

RESULTS ANALYSIS OF THE CONDUCTED RESEARCH

In order to gain insights into the impact of online presentations of Ohrid's tourist offer on tourists, especially potential ones, and to perceive how attractive and influential their content is, a questionnaire survey was conducted among 66 domestic and 123 foreign tourists on the Ohrid Riviera. 61% were male and 39% female respondents. The majority of them, 57%, were between the ages of 51 and 60.

Domestic tourists visit Ohrid more often, unlike foreign tourists who mostly come for the first time (50,4% of the respondents) or for the second time (30,9% of the respondents).

Chart 1. Interval of visiting Ohrid

In order to determine how many visitors came to satisfy their tourist needs, respondents were asked a question about the purposes of their visit. Their answers are presented in the following chart:

Chart 2. The purpose of tourist visit

Regarding the purpose of visiting Ohrid, foreign tourists mostly visit Ohrid for tourism purposes, and domestic tourists almost equal for tourism and business purposes.

In order to gain insight into how much respondents (especially foreign tourists) know about the values that they can visit and discover in Ohrid, the survey was focused on the length of their stay in Ohrid. The answers received are presented in Chart 3.

Chart 3. Length of tourist stay

From particular interest of the research was how visitors acquired information about the content of the tourist offer. The results presented in Chart 4 indicate that the majority of tourists, and especially foreign tourists, learned about the values of Ohrid from searching on internet portals.

Chart 4. Sources of information about Ohrid's tourist offer

Regarding the influence of propaganda content on tourists' decisions to visit Ohrid, tourists expressed the following views:

Chart 5. Influence of promotional content on the decision to purchase tourist services

The chart shows that a large proportion of tourists decided to visit Ohrid motivated by the content of promotional content, but also the percentage of

respondents which this promotional content has a partial or no influence on their decision is high.

Considering the attitudes of the guests that the promotion messages have influence on their decision to visit Ohrid, and most of them (especially the foreign tourists) were informed about Ohrid as a desired destination through internet network platforms, the holders of tourism development should place more creatively contents of the tourist values offered by Ohrid. Analyzing the promotional content of individual providers of tourist services in Ohrid, it can be conclude that there is a need for more innovative approach to presenting natural and anthropogenic elements as well the specificity of hospitality services.

CONCLUSION

The Internet is an international information network that is turning the world into a “global village.” It has ability to be a medium in promotional and communicative activity between different categories of tourism providers and actual and potential tourists. In today's modern business world, it is unthinkable to function without the Internet and new technologies that enter all spheres of socio-economic life. Internet has significant role especially in the tourism field, where today more than ever it is imperative for the tourist destinations to be present on the Internet, as well as on various social networks.

Due to the daily advancement of the Internet, the form and characteristics of its content, the creative processes, mechanisms for distribution and promotion are changing, as well models for sharing that content on the Internet. Internet content is used to find a large amount of accurate, precise, up-to-date information about one tourist place. This means that the tourist before the trip knows what to expect at the destination that want to visit.

All participants in the national and international tourism market are focused on global business, and thus on the large circle of different potential tourists. Therefore, the Internet and its basic services must be the main tool in implementing the overall marketing strategy in order to achieve the set business goals and make a profit, and this can only be achieved through continuous education that leads to an increase in the level of knowledge and technical skills.

Ohrid as a tourist destination must make more efforts and invest more resources for creating more innovative and creative promotional campaigns on Internet, especially on social networks, in order to attract more tourists by presenting its natural and anthropogenic elements as well the specificity of hospitality services.

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